

LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS
WITH SEMANTICS OF HUMAN CHARACTER AS AN EFFECTIVE
MEANS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation

The article deals with issues related to the linguocultural value of idioms of the English language, phraseological units with the semantics of a person's character and their special place and role in the study of the English language. The methodical use of idioms in many tasks and exercises to develop speaking skills, to expand vocabulary, develop creative abilities, translation skills and vocabulary skills is justified through examples reflecting the lexical diversity of idioms. A method for studying English idioms with the help of special exercises based on the semantic comparison of English and Uzbek idioms is described. The special importance of studying English idioms is substantiated, in comparison with the phraseological units of the native (Uzbek) language, which gives an additional opportunity for students to delve into the history, customs and traditions of the country of the language being studied, enrich themselves with universal moral values and form their views on the world around them with all its diversity.

Keywords: phraseological unit, idiom, character of a person, idioms of the English language, idioms of the Uzbek language, teaching idioms

Introduction. The study of foreign languages in modern society is becoming an inseparable component of the professional training of specialists of various profiles,

and the successful solution of professional growth issues and the expansion of contacts with foreign partners largely depend on the quality of their language training. Consequently, the secondary school and university are designed to provide a certain level of foreign language proficiency, which could allow them to continue studying the language during postgraduate education, as well as independently. The success of training largely depends on the methodology of the teacher of a foreign language, on his ability to use various modern methods in the context of solving specific educational problems.

Phraseological unit is an integral part of any language. In any language, phraseological units serve for the expressiveness of speech, its figurativeness, brightness and accuracy. The use of phraseological units gives liveliness to speech, helps to convey the meaning of the statement better and faster. Phraseological units are used by all people in everyday communication, by journalists when writing articles and reviews on various topics, by politicians, economists, analysts in official addresses and during interviews. That is why we note the importance and necessity of a detailed study of phraseological expressions. In the foreign linguistic tradition, phraseological units are usually called idioms. Idioms occupy an important place in the study of English, they are widely used by native speakers, and for learners of this language as a foreign language, they are often incomprehensible. Real knowledge of the English language implies the ability to speak, using expressions characteristic of this - idioms. After all, it is in colloquial speech that they are mostly used. It should be noted that in English and American linguistics, it is not the term "phraseological unit" that is more commonly used, but the so-called "set-expression", which means essentially the same thing, along with the latter, the concept of "idioms" is also used. In English linguistics, it does not have the narrow meaning of phraseological fusion, but denotes all set expressions in general. Idioms of the English language are stable expressions that have an independent meaning, usually not coinciding with the literal translation. The word "idiom" comes from the Greek "idíōma", which means "peculiarity, originality".

Where did they come from? Over the millennium of history, the English language has accumulated a large number of expressions that people have found successful, accurate and beautiful. With the help of idioms, the language becomes alive. The range of modern English idioms is wide and varied, most of them are borrowed from fiction and not only English. Linguists do not have a common opinion about what phraseology is and there is no unity of views on the composition of these units in the language. Some researchers (L.P. Smith, D. Seidl, W. McMordie V.P. Zhukov, V.N. Telia, N.M. Shansky and others) include stable combinations in phraseological units, others (N.N. Amosova, A.M. Babkin, A.I. Smirnitsky and others) - only certain groups. So, some linguists (including academician V.V. Vinogradov [1, pp. 140-161]) do not include proverbs, sayings and catchwords in the category of phraseological units, believing that they differ in their semantics and syntactic structure from phraseological units. Russian scientists N. N. Amosova and A. V. Kunin studied English phraseological units in historical and theoretical-linguistic aspects. In the scientific research of linguists and linguodidactics, some of the publications are devoted to various aspects of teaching idioms. Thus, part of the work is devoted to the study of idioms as an effective way to replenish vocabulary in English in order to master professional communicative competence [2, p.18-22], in particular, V.E. Borisenkov and M.P. Storozhenko in their work pay attention to the use of idioms and other colloquial universals to make written speech more emotional [3, pp. 202-205]. In the study by V.L. Malakhova, the features and expediency of applying the principles of cognitive linguistics to the study of phraseological units in general are considered in detail [4, P. 65-75]. Some authors pay attention to modern, but no less effective ways of studying idioms. So, according to D. Tafazoli and S. Shirimbu, the use of social networks, in particular Facebook, is one of such methods [5, p. 10-15].

Discussion. In the study of idioms, their different classifications play a major role. The most common classification of English phraseological units is thematic. For example, in the English-phraseological dictionary of A.V. Kunin [6, C. 272-332] there

are several idiomatic groups that are associated with a person and his character; with animals; with body parts with clothes; with a palette of colors; with products; with money; with color names with school and education; with household items; with the weather. The most interesting is the semantic group of English idioms with a component of describing a person's character. Character traits make up those essential properties of a person that determine one or another way of behavior, way of life. There are four groups of character traits in the system of personality relations [7, C. 665-678]:

- Person's attitude to other people (sociability, sensitivity and responsiveness, respect for other people, and opposite features - isolation, callousness, rudeness, contempt for people);

- Features showing a person's attitude to work, to his job (hard work, accuracy, tendency to creativity, conscientiousness in work, responsible attitude to the cause, initiative, perseverance, and the opposite features - laziness, tendency to routine work, dishonesty in work, irresponsible attitude to business, passivity);

- Features that show how a person feels about himself (self-esteem, sense of pride and the self-criticism associated with it, modesty, and opposing traits: conceit, sometimes arrogance, arrogance - resentment, shyness, egocentrism - as inclination to view at the center of events oneself and one's own experiences, egoism - tending to care primarily for one's own personal good);

- Features characterizing a person's attitude to things: (neatness or sloppiness, careful or negligent handling of things).

For example, in connection with other people in the English language increasingly are presented such character traits as "pride" - to look down one's nose at somebody; with one's nose in the; get on one's high horse; to get a swelled; "cruelty" - as hard as nails, the cat-and-mouse game; "insensibility"- thick-skinned, be hard on; "duplicity" - butter wouldn't melt in one's mouth, "insolence" - come (or do) the heavy over, "vanity" - get on one's horse, "arrogance" - all know it, "isolation" - person, a lone wolf; "decency" (good as), gold, "honesty" - a straight-line man, salt of the earth,

clean hands. In relation to the person to himself in the English language predominates “cunning” - (as) cunning (или sly) as a fox, an old fox; “cowardice”- to have a yellow streak, afraid of one's own shadow and “stupidity”- chicken-brained, to be thick , “shyness” - can't say bo (boh или boo) to a goose, “selfishness”- give one's own fish, “cheerfulness”- (as) lively (or merry) as a grig. In relation to work “diligence” - be as busy as a bee, “proactivity” - - mover and shaker, “laziness” - - couch potato, “passivity” - let the grass grow under one's feet, cumber the ground.

Studying phraseological units, we can observe how stable phrases reflect the attitude of the people to certain moral qualities of a person. We also observe which character traits are most important to people, which are of the greatest value to them. Idioms are not a separate part of the language that can either be used or not. Idioms form an essential part of the general vocabulary of the English language, which is now undergoing great changes. To better understand the language you are learning, you need to understand what meaning idioms have in that particular language. It is necessary to find out the hidden meaning inherent in a certain expression. Learning a language with idioms can be tricky, but if you look at it from the other side, it becomes obvious that with the help of learning idioms, we enrich our vocabulary, develop the ability to listen, speak and write competently. In addition, the study of idiom - it can be a very fun activity, which is perceived more as a rest than a hard work. The main thing is being able to properly teach this kind of work to students. At a certain stage of learning the language acutely felt the need to learn idiom - speech without the use of which is often perceived as pupil, because it looks too «academic» and devoid of emotional color. This problem may seem intractable because there is no effective system for studying and using idioms. The English curriculum does not always include idioms. As a rule, this aspect is given very little time and attention, due to the fact that the work program is so saturated with grammatical materials and the study of lexical minimum that there is not always enough time to work out such speech. Despite numerous studies on linguodidactics, the question remains how to make the process of

learning idioms effective, functional and interesting for both students and teachers. We came to the conclusion that a productive study of idioms is possible if you follow a comprehensive methodology that systematically includes work with idioms in a foreign (English) language course:

1. Separation of idioms by themes, which will greatly facilitate memorization;
2. Study through search of analogues in the Uzbek language;
3. Assimilation of idioms in a context to understand in which situation the use of an expression would be appropriate;
4. More detailed study of the origins of idioms;
5. Learning from exercise and speech;
6. The use of new technologies in the form of useful applications that also facilitate the process of learning English idioms.

As part of this approach, we have developed a number of exercises that allow us to learn English idioms effectively, with subsequent application in written and spoken language. The analysis of the different types of exercise leads us to the conclusion that it is necessary to select an idiom strictly dosing quantity, since it is easiest to synchronize the memory of idioms for a long time in an associative way, So you have to do different kinds of tasks to use the same idioms. The following are excerpts from the author's set of exercises using selected idioms.

Exercise 1. Learn these phraseological units:

what the heart thinks the tongue speaks; be not as green as one is cabbage-looking; (as) gentle as a dove; hang up one's fiddle when one comes home; pick a hole (или holes) in; be free, white and (over) twentyone; have light fingers (have sticky fingers); go through fire and water; a fool always rushes to the fore; fall (или land) on one's feet.

Exercise 2. Underline phraseological units and translate sentences.

1. He did not entirely hang his fiddle up when he came home [6, C.272].
2. You're free, white and twenty-one. He couldn't make you go there [6, C. 298].

3. I ain't the sort to be taken in by his gaff. I may look a fool... but I'm not as green as I'm cabbage-looking [6, C. 332].

4. She's musical to her finger-tips, gentle as a dove, and a miracle of unselfishness... (W. S. Maugham. "Complete Short Stories", "The Voice of the Turtle").

5. There's no pleasin' some folk. Ye werena [= were not] satisfied with Mamma, and now ye're startin' to pick holes in my Nancy (A. J. Cronin. "Hatter's Castle", book III, ch. 2).

6. He doesn't have light fingers. Not even the Signora Coogan could say that he touched her jewels or anything else that she hadn't presented him with. (T. Williams. "The Roman Spring of Mrs Stone", Kenk).

Exercise 3. Give a description in English to these phraseological units of the Uzbek language: кампир дарди ғўзада; анойи эмас; қўйдаи ювош; қўча хандон, уй зиндон; тирноқ тагидан кир қидиради; эркин қуш; қўли эгри; сув келса, симиради, тош келса кемиради; тентак тўрини бермас; сувдан қуруқ чиқади.

Exercise 4. For these idioms, choose the appropriate phraseological units of the Uzbek language: what the heart thinks the tongue speaks; be not as green as one is cabbage-looking; (as) gentle as a dove; hang ap one's fiddle when one comes home; pick a hole (или holes); be free, white and (over) twentyone; have light fingers (have sticky fingers); go through fire and water; a fool always rushes to the fore; fall (или land) on one's feet.

Conclusion. The lexical diversity of idioms allows them to be used in many tasks and exercises to develop speaking skills, to expand vocabulary, to develop creative abilities, translation skills and ability to work with vocabulary. Modern methods of teaching foreign languages dictate the application of approaches that form not only language professional competence, but also expand the general outlook and cultural level of students. In the process of learning English idioms, students use a multifaceted range of their competencies, comparing idioms with phraseological units of their native

(Uzbek) language, delving into the history, customs and traditions of the country of the language being studied. At the same time, students are enriched with universal moral values and form their views on the world around them with all its diversity. In addition, by studying the idioms of any language, we study the culture and national character of the people who speak it. The country value of idiomatic expressions lies in their authenticity. Analyzing them, you can trace the history of the country, partially acquainted with its customs and traditions, get an idea of the mentality of the people speaking the language. When studying idioms, many authors point out the fact that they can more easily than any other language unit to accumulate and store information about the past, culture and traditions of the people.

References

1. Vinogradov V.V. On the main types of phraseological units in the Russian language // Selected Works. Lexicology and lexicography. - M. - 1977. - S. 140-161
2. Baskakova N.S. Studying idioms as an effective way to replenish vocabulary in English // Innovative technologies in technology and education VII International scientific and practical conference: Sat. Art. resp. ed. M. I. Melikhova. - 2015. - S. 18-22.
3. Borisenkova V.E., Storozhenko M.P. The use of clichés, idioms and phraseological units as a means of increasing the emotionality of written speech // Philological Sciences. Intellectual potential of the 21st century: stages of knowledge. Novosibirsk. - 2011. - No. 8. - S. 202-205.
4. Malakhova V.L. Types of Phraseologically Represented Concepts in English. Nauchnye Vedomosti of the Belgorod State University. Series: Humanities. - 2017. - T. 33. - No. 7 (256). - S. 65-75.
5. Tafazoli D., Shirimbu S. Social networks. Using Facebook when teaching English idioms // World of linguistics and communication: electronic scientific journal. - 2013. - T. 1. - No. 30. - S. 10-15.

6. Kunin A.V. English-Russian phraseological dictionary. - M: "Russian language" 1984 -942 p.
7. Rubinstein S. L. Fundamentals of General Psychology - St. Petersburg: Publishing House "Piter", 2000 - 712 p.